

HyDelta 3

WP3A – Greenhouse potential of hydrogen emissions from the grid

D3A.1 – Emission amounts

D3A.2 – Priority of reduction

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Corresponding author

Corresponding author	Nard Vermeltfoort
Affiliation	Kiwa
Email address	Nard.Vermeltfoort@kiwa.com

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Executive summary

Hydrogen is an indirect greenhouse gas. The word “indirect” indicates that while hydrogen itself does not contribute to global warming, hydrogen in the atmosphere causes other greenhouse gases (mostly methane) to stay in the atmosphere longer. The mechanisms in the atmosphere are complex and the effects of hydrogen in the atmosphere can only be modelled. Because different assumptions can be made during modelling, the extent to which hydrogen contributes to the greenhouse effect is currently ambiguous.

Hydrogen is one of the promising green energy carriers aiding the creation of a sustainable energy system. The Dutch hydrogen grid will exist of newly installed pipelines and repurposed pipelines from the current natural gas grids. With the transportation of energy, energy is lost, for instance due to leakages if the pipeline is damaged. The main objective of this HyDelta 3.0 work package is to give an indication of the amount of Dutch hydrogen transportation and distribution emissions and the expected contribution to global warming of the atmosphere. It then briefly discusses the best emission reduction steps.

The expected yearly hydrogen emission of the Dutch hydrogen grids in 2050 is expected to be between 0.7 and 2.4 million kg. When the fugitive emission of the highest scenario (2.4 million kg hydrogen) is compared to the current gas grid, a CO₂ equivalent reduction of 92% is achieved. The hydrogen emission values were obtained by multiplying the current emissions from the natural gas networks by the leakage factors of hydrogen and the predicted grid lengths. The emission values of natural gas were based on the OGMP reporting, provided annually by the Dutch DSOs and TSO. The leakage factors were obtained from previous HyDelta research.

The grids of today are not the grids of the future. Assumptions have been made for the extent of the future hydrogen grid. These numbers are taken from the “Netbeheer Nederland's I13050” report. The upper value (2.4 million kg hydrogen emission) is based on the I13050 international scenario. Here 83% of the current natural gas grid is converted to hydrogen, which is the highest predicted amount. New grids will have fewer losses due to technological advances. These advances have only been taken into account to a limited extent as they are not known yet. Other assumptions were made assuming the most realistic future possible. Where this was impossible, the worst-case scenario was assumed.

Regardless of the uncertainties from the current period until 2050, this research aimed to provide an indication of the hydrogen emissions that could take place in the future. With this indication, a vision can be drawn up that provides a good consideration in the proportionality of measures that can be taken to reduce hydrogen emissions.

Samenvatting

Waterstof is een indirect broeikasgas. Het woord indirect geeft aan dat waterstof zelf geen bijdrage geeft aan de opwarming van de aarde. Echter, wanneer waterstof in de atmosfeer komt, zorgt dit ervoor dat andere broeikasgassen (met name methaan) langer in de atmosfeer verblijven. De mechanismes in de atmosfeer zijn complex en de effecten van waterstof in de atmosfeer kunnen alleen worden gemodelleerd. Doordat er verschillende aannames gedaan kunnen worden tijdens het opstellen van modellen, is de mate waarin waterstof bijdraagt momenteel niet eenduidig vastgesteld.

Waterstof is een van de veelbelovende groene energiedragers om een duurzaam energiesysteem te creëren. Het Nederlandse waterstofnet zal bestaan uit nieuw aangelegde pijpleidingen en hergebruikte pijpleidingen uit de huidige aardgasnetten. Bij het transport van energie gaat energie verloren, bijvoorbeeld door lekkages als de pijpleiding beschadigd raakt. Dit HyDelta 3.0 werkpakket heeft als hoofddoel om een indicatie te geven van de hoeveelheid Nederlandse waterstofemissies door transport en distributie, en de verwachte bijdrage aan de opwarming van de atmosfeer. Daarna wordt kort behandeld wat de beste emissiereductie stappen zijn.

De verwachte jaarlijkse waterstofemissie van de Nederlandse waterstofnetten in 2050 zal tussen de 0,7 en 2,4 miljoen kg zijn. Wanneer het scenario met de grootste hoeveelheid waterstoftransport (2,4 miljoen kg waterstof emissie), wordt vergeleken met het huidige aardgasnet, zal de CO₂ equivalent emissie met ongeveer 92% afnemen. Deze waarden zijn verkregen door de huidige uitstoot van de aardgasnetten te vermenigvuldigen met de lekfactoren van waterstof en de verwachte netwerk lengte. Voor de uitstootwaarden van aardgas is uitgegaan van de OGMP rapportage die de Nederlandse DSO's en TSO jaarlijks opleveren. De lekfactoren zijn verkregen door eerder HyDelta onderzoek.

De netten van nu zijn niet de netten van de toekomst. Er zijn aannames gedaan voor de afmetingen van het toekomstige waterstofnet. Deze zijn overgenomen uit het I13050 rapport van Netbeheer Nederland. De bovenste waarde (2,4 miljoen kg waterstofemissie) is gebaseerd op het internationale scenario I13050. Hier wordt 83% van het huidige aardgasnet omgezet naar waterstof, wat de hoogst voorspelde hoeveelheid is. Nieuwe netten zullen minder verliezen hebben door technologische vooruitgang. Deze vooruitgangen konden slechts beperkt meegenomen worden omdat ze nog niet bekend zijn. Andere aannames zijn gedaan op basis van een zo realistisch mogelijke toekomst. Waar dit onmogelijk was, is uitgegaan van het slechtst denkbare scenario.

Ongeacht de onzekerheden van nu tot 2050, is het onderzoek erop gericht om een indicatie te geven van de waterstofemissies die in de toekomst plaatsvinden. Met deze indicatie kan een visie worden opgesteld die een goede afweging maakt in de proportionaliteit van maatregelen die genomen kunnen worden om de waterstof emissie te beperken.

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1. Introduction

Peer reviewed literature indicates that hydrogen is a greenhouse gas. The global warming potential of hydrogen varied over time as more research was done. One of the most recent studies indicates a GWP₁₀₀, which means the global warming potential of hydrogen in a 100-year time-horizon, of 11.6 ± 2.8 [1]. Compared to a GWP₁₀₀ of 29.8 ± 11 for methane this seems to be one third of the total emission [2]. However, in practice this is more complicated as density and leak rates also play a role.

As carbon-neutral hydrogen is regarded as a sustainable energy carrier, the message that hydrogen is a greenhouse gas might seem contradictory to some. However, the distinction has to be made between hydrogen as an energy carrier (preferably made from zero-emission sources) and hydrogen as a fugitive gas in the atmosphere. While the first form of hydrogen is very good replacement of fossil fuels, the second form is an unwanted side effect of the transition to a hydrogen energy system.

It is inevitable that during transport of energy a part of it is lost. In this report the losses that are related to transporting hydrogen through a pipeline and emitted into the atmosphere are investigated. In the Dutch natural gas system these type of losses are less than 0.1% of the transported volume. Upstream (production) and downstream (utilization) losses are not taken into account. Although the entire hydrogen value chain should investigate and minimize losses, this work package focusses on the transportation and distribution network of the TSO and DSOs in the Netherlands. Nevertheless, the calculations, findings and assumptions can also be used in analysis of other parts in the hydrogen value chain.

There is a lot known about emissions of gases from gas grids. In recent developments, European legislation is becoming more stringent to take emission mitigating measures to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. DSOs and TSOs across Europe must take measures to quantify and reduce methane emissions. This increased the amount of research on (fugitive) methane emission. With the energy transition towards a sustainable energy supply an option is to transform parts of the natural gas grid into a hydrogen grid.

Currently, with the limited usage of hydrogen, the cumulative greenhouse effect of hydrogen emission is relatively limited due to scale limitations. However, this may change when the hydrogen production, distribution and usage increases in the coming years. In order to have the least amount of climate impact from the hydrogen emission, a quantification of the expected amount is needed. This can then serve as a basis for emission-mitigating measures. A similar approach is already being taken with methane emissions of the current natural gas grid. As (part of) the pipelines which are currently in use for transporting natural gas will be transformed into transporting hydrogen, the methane emission data can be used as a good basis for an estimation of the hydrogen emissions from the transport and distribution grid.

Please note that this report is written in the pyramid principle structure. The titles of the chapters are composed of the main conclusion from that chapter. The substantiation on this conclusion is further specified in the forthcoming chapter. The conclusion can therefore be read in the Table of contents.

1.1 Hydrogen is an indirect greenhouse gas

Hydrogen is widely recognized as an important future energy carrier. If hydrogen is produced from renewable energy sources, it is possible to build an energy system with near zero emissions of pollutants and greenhouse gases [3].

Hydrogen is expected to be a key instrument to meet the European Union (EU) Green Deal main objective (i.e., climate neutrality by 2050). To align with this objective, the EU is planning to ramp up renewable hydrogen production by 2030.

Hydrogen (H₂) is the smallest of all the molecular gases in the atmosphere. In atmospheric conditions it is relatively unreactive and behaves as a well-mixed trace gas in the troposphere. Hydrogen is a homonuclear diatomic molecule (it lacks a dipole) and therefore it does not absorb infrared radiation (IR) and so it is not a direct radiatively active gas [5]. With the increasing global interest in hydrogen to replace fossil fuels, more attention is being paid to potential leakage of hydrogen into the atmosphere and its environmental consequences [5].

Hydrogen is not a direct greenhouse gas (GHG), but its chemical reactions with other gasses change the lifetime of greenhouse gases like methane (CH₄), stratospheric water vapour and aerosols. Hydrogen is called an indirect GHG because it elongates the lifetime of GHGs (mainly methane and water vapour) already present in the atmosphere. In the existing value chain, there is very little data on the magnitude of these leakages and how this will evolve in a future growing hydrogen economy. Additionally, there is not a lot of literature on the environmental implications of leakages due to transporting hydrogen in a large scale gas grid. In this study, efforts are made to quantify the hydrogen leakage and to come up with measures to mitigate the emissions.

1.2 Hydrogen released into the atmosphere increases the lifetime of other greenhouse gasses

Present day hydrogen presence is about 530 ppbv [1]. Sources of hydrogen include biomass burning, fossil fuel combustion, biological nitrogen fixation, atmospheric photo-oxidation of methane & volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and possible geological sources. Hydrogen is removed from the atmosphere by biological uptake in soils and atmospheric oxidation by the hydroxyl radical (OH). The largest uptake and the most uncertain in the atmospheric hydrogen budget is the soil uptake, which in many studies accounts from 65 – 85% of the total hydrogen sink [6, 7].

Figure 1: Global hydrogen budget [7]

Figure 1 from a JRC report on hydrogen emission, presents the atmospheric hydrogen budget combining the ranges for the different sources and sinks [7]. Sources of hydrogen are depicted in red, while the sinks are in green. The biggest sink for hydrogen is by soil uptake.

As mentioned previously, hydrogen is not a direct greenhouse gas. But hydrogen is involved in atmospheric chemical reactions that affect the lifetime and abundances of other gases that have an impact on the climate [6] and is thus an indirect greenhouse gas. Four main climate impacts are associated with increased hydrogen levels:

1. Longer methane (CH₄) lifetime and hence increased methane abundances
2. Enhanced production of tropospheric ozone (O₃) and change in stratospheric O₂
3. Increased stratospheric water vapour (H₂O) production
4. Changes in production of certain aerosols

The most important chemical reaction driving these impacts is the destruction of hydrogen by OH:

OH is the most important and a powerful oxidant in the atmosphere. Oxidation by OH is an important sink of hydrogen, CH₄ and other components in the atmosphere. Hydrogen here acts as an indirect GHG because of its reaction with OH which depletes the oxidising capacity of the troposphere and increases the atmospheric lifetimes of all the other trace gases which have OH oxidation as a main feature of their life cycle, such as methane. This leads to increased lifetime of CH₄ which results in increased greenhouse warming, and in turn, increased tropospheric ozone which is also a GHG [8].

Figure 2 represents the changes in the radiative forces measured by Maria Sand et al., in one of their experiments using the OsloCTM chemistry model [1]. In the below figure, methane (green bars), ozone (yellow), stratospheric water vapour (purple) and aerosols (red) are represented.

Figure 2: Changes in the radiative forcing due to 1 Tg flux of hydrogen [1]

1.3 In this research hydrogen emissions are theoretically calculated

The objective of this research is to provide a firm programme position on the need for future emission-mitigating measures of hydrogen in transport and distribution grids. The goal of this work package is to provide insight in hydrogen emissions and the resulting global warming potential expected by transporting hydrogen in the transport and distribution grids. The lack of information on this topic gave rise to a societal discussion on the advisability of a hydrogen economy. The expected result of this short report is to summarize the theoretical research.

The main research questions are:

Which amount of hydrogen emission is to be expected from transports through the transport and distribution grids?

and

To what extent and with what priority and urgency should emission mitigating measures for hydrogen transport and distribution be taken by the TSO and DSOs?

To answer these questions, theoretical research is done. A scan of scientific papers on hydrogen greenhouse potential and scan of known emission sources in the methane emission programme is made and the results can be found in chapter 3.

To quantify the expected hydrogen emissions and its likely greenhouse effect, results from the currently running methane emission programme (OGMP) are used. In this program the methane emission of the natural gas grids is quantified. This data is used to calculate current natural gas emission which can be converted to hydrogen emission. For this we use previous (practical) HyDelta results to determine the leak rates. This can be found in chapter 2.

To predict the future gas grid length, scenarios and rollout plans are researched and taken into account. These can be found in chapter 4.

1.4 Other research activities are involved where possible

The topic of hydrogen emissions from gas transport is also part of Groenvermogen Nederland (GVNL) WP2. However, WP2 of GVNL has a wider scope while this HyDelta work package 3A focusses on emissions from the grid. The GVNL work package 2 was starting around the same time, however the planned release of the GVNL work package results is around Q1 2026, therefore the HyDelta work package could serve as an input for the GVNL work package.

Additionally, researchers from the RUG and the WUR were interviewed on this topic. The scope of their current research differs from emission of the grids, however hydrogen emission and its effect is being investigated. The researchers mentioned that a global hydrogen concentration monitoring system does not yet exist, but should be implemented as soon as possible. The urgency exists to set a baseline before the predicted uptake of hydrogen. The global system should be aimed at monitoring the increase in atmospheric hydrogen concentration and its effect on the climate. This urgency and necessity of such a system should be acknowledged by the entire hydrogen value chain, including (hydrogen) grid operators.

2. Hydrogen transportation has less than one 10th of the global warming impact compared to natural gas transportation

It is estimated that a total of 0.7 to 2.4 million kg of hydrogen emission per year will be emitted due to hydrogen pipeline transport in The Netherlands in 2050. The largest part is emitted by the distribution network, the transport network only emits a small part of the total. 2.4 million kg of hydrogen emission corresponds to roughly 28 million kg CO₂ equivalent on a GWP100 scale (factor of 11.6 CO₂eq/kgH₂). On a GWP20 scale (30.0 CO₂eq/kgH₂) it is around 72 million kg CO₂ equivalent. The chosen GWP values and their uncertainty is further explained in chapter 3. Compared to the current natural gas grid, this accounts for a 92% reduction in CO₂ equivalent fugitives of the network. Put differently, it is expected highest hydrogen use scenario, the future hydrogen grid emits less than one tenth of the CO₂ equivalent emissions of the current natural gas grid. If the current grid would be fully repurposed (so 100% of the current grid) it would mean a reduction of 90% in the CO₂ equivalent emission. To put these numbers in a different perspective; 28 million kg CO₂ equivalent emission is equal to having a powerplant such as the Eemshaven operate on coal for around 16 hours.

Obviously, a number of assumptions are made to come to these emission numbers. In this chapter all assumptions will be discussed. In the next chapter the emission metrics are explained, and more details will be given for when to use which metric.

2.1 The hydrogen emission per year is estimated between 0.6 and 2.2 million kg for the DSOs in 2050

It is estimated a total of 2,200,000 kg of hydrogen per year will be emitted to the atmosphere due to the hydrogen transport in the distribution grid in the highest use scenario. In this highest use scenario 97% of the current natural gas grid will be repurposed for hydrogen distribution. For the scenario with the lowest amount of hydrogen distribution, where only 31% of the grid is transporting hydrogen, the estimated fugitive emission is 0.6 million kg of hydrogen per year. The scenarios are elaborated in chapter 4.

2.2 The hydrogen emission per year is estimated around 0.21 million kg for the TSO in 2050

It is estimated that the TSO emits around 210,000 kg hydrogen emissions per year in 2050. In 2030 the expected rate is 10,000 kg, mainly because it is still in a roll-out phase by then. Due to the nature of the grids there are several reasons why the TSO emits less than the DSO although the transported volume is larger. A big factor is that there are no 3rd party damages incorporated into the emission number of the TSO as due to effective mitigating measures did not occur in the Netherlands. Furthermore, the grid length (excluding the service lines) is roughly one tenth compared to the DSO networks and in this length the TSO has far less connections. Because the TSO utilizes thick-walled steel pipes, permeation is negligible. Also, LDAR campaigns are performed more often and are more stringent, again due to the nature and risks involved with transporting gas at high pressures.

2.3 Methane fugitives are chosen as a basis for this study

There are different ways to estimate the leakage rate of a gas grid. For this study it was chosen to take the methane emissions data as a basis. Currently methane emissions of the Dutch natural gas grid is a well-researched topic. The Dutch DSOs and TSO committed to the Oil and Gas Methane

Partnership (OGMP) reporting. The OGMP is a worldwide initiative of the United Nations to obtain a global overview of the methane emissions and a pathway towards methane emission reduction. Every year an increase in the quality of the quantification of the emissions is demanded by the OGMP to ensure that the reported emissions become a better representation for the actual emissions. The EU mostly copies this approach in legislation. The DSOs are now in the third year of reporting and still make improvements in the reported emissions.

Given the GHG effect of methane, significant efforts are dedicated to mitigate fugitive emissions throughout the natural gas value chain. However, not all the methods are equally effective. Thus, the cost-effectiveness of each approach should be carefully considered compared to the outcome. This principle, known as “proportionality”, aims to identify which element of the grid should be optimized to achieve the highest fugitive emission reduction with the least amount of investment. Experimental research, measurements and statistical analyses remain ongoing to further increase the knowledge about methane emissions and the proportionality in mitigation measures. As previously mentioned, the methane emission data from the OGMP dataset is used as a baseline for this emission study.

2.4 Volumetric leak rates for hydrogen are higher than for methane

Leaks are always present in a gas distribution system. This can be present due to installation error, aging, 3rd party damages, permeation, etc. In this research we categorise the leaks into 3 different types of leaks: Permeation, “regular” leaks and 3rd party damages, see Table 1. Hydrogen is less viscous than methane. The hydrogen flow (in volume) through an orifice is therefore higher than methane flowing through the same orifice. The (leak) factor depends on the type of flow. For small leaks, the flow is laminar, leading to a leak factor of 1.5 for hydrogen. For larger leaks the flow is turbulent, leading to a leak factor of 3 for hydrogen [9]. The leak factors on regular leaks and damages found in literature are based on volumetric flow of Dutch natural gas. Fugitive emissions are reported in mass, therefore the densities of natural gas and hydrogen are used to calculate a mass based leak factor. Because of the exceptionally low density of hydrogen (0.09 kg/Nm³ compared to 0.833 kg/Nm³ for natural gas), the mass-based factor is a lot lower.

Table 1: Leak factors of hydrogen compared to natural gas

	Volume based (-)	Mass based (-)
Permeation:	4	0,55
Regular leaks:	1,5	0,16
Damages:	3	0,32

Permeation is the effect of molecules traveling through a solid material. In this case the molecules are methane or hydrogen and the solid is the pipe in which the gas flows. Several research outcomes indicate that hydrogen permeates a plastic type pipe 3-5 times more than methane. An exact number is hard to give as there are many variables and different papers publish different results on the same type of tests. However, a reasonable assumption is that hydrogen permeates 4 times as much as methane for PE/PVC pipelines. As this literature is based on methane, the density of methane (0.656 kg/Nm³) is used to calculate the mass based factor of 0.55. The distribution grid consists mainly of PVC/PE pipes, which is why this number is taken for the entire distribution grid. Metallic pipeline material (steel, cast iron, copper, etc.) have permeation factors that are 2 to 6 orders lower. These types of materials are also utilized in the distribution network, however their combined permeation is very small and therefore permeation of these lines is not taken into account. The TSO utilizes thick-walled steel pipes for most of its entire grid, in which the permeation is negligible.

The second type consists of “regular” leaks. These are leaks found during leak searching. These are regarded as relatively small leaks, and therefore the leak factor for laminar leaks (1.5) is used for this category. The leaks can develop over time due to corrosion, material degradation, alteration of the surrounding soil, etc. This is the majority of the fugitive emissions in this category. Additionally other small sources (such as small vents when installing a new pipeline) are added in this number. This combination of “regular” leaks represents about half of all fugitive emissions.

The third type is represented by 3rd party damages. These are incidents where pipelines are damaged by 3rd parties, usually due to digging activities. Because these can be significant leaks, the leak factor for turbulent leaks (3) is applied. For the TSO, mitigating measures are taken to prevent 3rd party damages, which have proven to be successful so far. However, some direct outflow emission is unavoidable for the TSO, in which case the leak factor of 3 is used for the calculations.

For the DSO, leaks from 3rd party damages have the largest contribution, followed by regular leaks, permeation is by far the smallest. For the TSO, fugitive emissions at the transmission stations have the largest contribution, followed by underground storage facilities, and for 2050, compressor stations.

3. The indirect greenhouse effects of hydrogen can only be modeled

3.1 Selecting the right emission metric is important for the goal

The hydrogen molecule is not a direct GHG since the lack of a dipole molecule that prevents the absorption of IR. However, hydrogen acts as an indirect GHG as mentioned previously. To better understand the climate effects of hydrogen, its radiative forcing is compared to CO₂ (the reference climate forcing agent). There are lots of existing measures to capture the global warming potential:

- 1. Global Warming Potential (GWP)** – The Global Warming Potential (GWP) was developed to allow comparison of the global warming impact of different gases. It is a measure how much energy the emissions of 1 ton of a gas will absorb over a given period of time, relative to the emissions of 1 ton of CO₂. The larger the GWP, the more warming effects it has on earth compared to CO₂ over that period of time. There are many time periods use to indicate GWP like GWP20, GWP100 & GWP500. This means the GWP is compared over a time of 20, 100 & 500 years. For example, methane (CH₄) has a GWP100 of 27-30. This means that 1 ton of CH₄ emission can cause global warming equivalence of around 27-30 tonnes emission of CO₂ when evaluated over 100 years [10].
- 2. (Effective) Radiative Forcing (ERF)** – Radiative Forcing has been used to compare and rank the drivers of past & future climate changes. Effective Radiative Forcing (ERF) is now the most widely adopted since it has been found to be the best predictor of the resulting climate response, measured by global-mean surface-air temperature change (T). ERF quantifies the energy gained or lost by the Earth system following an imposed perturbation (for instance in GHGs, aerosols or solar irradiance). ERF is determined by the change in the net downward radiative flux at the top-of-atmosphere after the system has adjusted to the perturbation but excluding the radiative response to changes in the surface temperature [11]. ERFs are often expressed in W/m². Positive ERF value indicates a net warming effect on the climate, while negative values indicate a cooling effect.
- 3. Global Temperature Potential (GTP)** - An alternative metric used to measure the impact of different GHGs is the Global Temperature Potential (GTP). The GWP measures the heat absorbed over a given time period due to the emission of gas and the GTP is a measure of the temperature changes at the end of a given time period (relative to CO₂). IPCC defines GTP as the ratio between the global mean surface temperature change at a given future time horizon following an emission of a compound (hydrogen in this case) relative to a reference gas (CO₂ in this case). Even though, GTP metric has a potential advantage over GWP as it is more directly related to the surface temperature change but the calculation of GTP is more complicated as it requires modelling the concentration increase of GHGs and how quickly the system responds.

The above mentioned 3 measures are being proposed to determine the GHG potential of hydrogen. The choice of the metrics to adopt when assessing the climate impact of hydrogen is often a source of controversy. Every metric has flaws, and the choice must depend on the purpose of the analysis. For this reason, the latest IPCC reports do not recommend an emission metric to report the emissions but rather aggregating them as CO₂eq. The latest IPCC report chose the GWP100 metric to aggregate emission in order to align with decision under the Paris Agreement Rulebook. It is decided that this

research will follow the approach of the IPCC and therefore this report reports hydrogen emission the advised emission mass along with GWP100 and the GWP20 CO₂ equivalent.

3.2 Global Warming Potential is used to compare different GHGs

GWP is used to show the effect of different GHGs on the climate over a period of time. As mentioned earlier, GWP is based on CO₂ equivalence, hence CO₂ has a GWP of 1. With this baseline, researchers are able to compare GHGs on a common basis to determine what will have more or less impact on the climate.

Each GHG has a different capacity for capturing & re-radiating outside the atmosphere and thereby contributing to radiative forcing. **Fout! Verwijzingsbron niet gevonden.** illustrates the process. Therefore, GWPs act as a kind of “exchange rate” for GHG, converting them into CO₂equivalent (CO₂eq) to compare their climate change impacts [12].

Figure 3: A simplified model of the natural greenhouse effect [3]

GWPs are based on different timeframes. The timeframes are the period of time over which the impacts are spread or integrated and used to compare the atmospheric energy trapped by a specific gas [13]. Using different timeframes does not change the amount of GHG emitted, but it changes the climate impact being estimated, see also Table 2.

- **Carbon di-Oxide (CO₂)** - CO₂ has a GWP of 1, as this is the gas used as a reference. CO₂ is a long-lived gas. While much of CO₂ can be absorbed by the oceans within centuries, the remaining CO₂ can stay in the atmosphere for thousands of years [14].
- **Methane (CH₄)** – The estimated GWP100 is around 29.8 [2]. Methane emitted today lasts about a decade on average, which is much less time than CO₂. But on the other hand, CH₄ absorbs more energy/heat than CO₂. The net effect of shorted lifetime and higher energy absorption is reflected in the GWP.
- **Nitrous Oxide (N₂O)** – The estimated GWP100 is around 273 [2]. Emitted N₂O will remain in the atmosphere for over a hundred years.

- **Fluorocarbons** CFCs, HFCs, HCFCs, PFCs and SF6 are sometimes called high-GWP gases as the GWP for these gases can be in thousands.

In Table 2 also the GTP (Global Temperature change Potential) and CGTP (Combined Global Temperature change Potential) are given on 2 different timescales (50 years and 100 years). GTP quantifies the surface temperature change from the emission of one kg of a gas relative to carbon dioxide [15]. CGTP directly compares the temperature change of a short-lived gas step-change emission to the temperature change of a carbon dioxide pulse. Both are relatively new metrics and will not be used further in this report.

Table 2: Different environmental effect numbers for several gasses (Table 7.15 from IPCC AR6 WGI) [2]

Species	Lifetime (Years)	Radiative Efficiency (W m ⁻² ppb ⁻¹)	GWP-20	GWP-100	GWP-500	GTP-50	GTP-100	CGTP-50 (years)	CGTP-100 (years)
CO ₂	Multiple	1.33 ± 0.16 × 10 ⁻⁵	1.	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000		
CH ₄ -fossil	11.8 ± 1.8	5.7 ± 1.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	82.5 ± 25.8	29.8 ± 11	10.0 ± 3.8	13.2 ± 6.1	7.5 ± 2.9	2823 ± 1060	3531 ± 1385
CH ₄ -non fossil	11.8 ± 1.8	5.7 ± 1.4 × 10 ⁻⁴	79.7 ± 25.8	27.0 ± 11	7.2 ± 3.8	10.4 ± 6.1	4.7 ± 2.9	2675 ± 1057	3228 ± 1364
N ₂ O	109 ± 10	2.8 ± 1.1 × 10 ⁻³	273 ± 118	273 ± 130	130 ± 64	290 ± 140	233 ± 110		
HFC-32	5.4 ± 1.1	1.1 ± 0.2 × 10 ⁻¹	2693 ± 842	771 ± 292	220 ± 87	181 ± 83	142 ± 51	78,175 ± 29,402	92,888 ± 36,534
HFC-134a	14.0 ± 2.8	1.67 ± 0.32 × 10 ⁻¹	4144 ± 1160	1526 ± 577	436 ± 173	733 ± 410	306 ± 119	146,670 ± 53,318	181,408 ± 71,365
CFC-11	52.0 ± 10.4	2.91 ± 0.65 × 10 ⁻¹	8321 ± 2419	6226 ± 2297	2093 ± 865	6351 ± 2342	3536 ± 1511		
PFC-14	50,000	9.89 ± 0.19 × 10 ⁻²	5301 ± 1395	7380 ± 2430	10,587 ± 3692	7660 ± 2464	9055 ± 3128		

3.3 There is no consensus on the correct GWP for hydrogen

The above mentioned gases are considered a GHG according to the Kyoto protocol. As mentioned earlier, hydrogen is not a direct GHG but instead seen as an indirect GHG due to its chemical alterations in the atmosphere.

The GWP measurements of hydrogen have not been as prevalently researched as that of other GHGs like CH₄, N₂O etc. Currently, there are around 3 to 4 model estimates for the GWP of hydrogen. The most prominent and new research (see below) are going to be discussed here.

- 1) Radiative forcing calculated by Paulot et al., (2021) [12].
- 2) STOCHM-CRI estimation by Derwent et al., (2020) [5].
- 3) Multi-model assessment done by Maria Sand et al., (2023) [1].

Models can have either an emission- or concentration-driven approach. Concentration-based models typically prescribe a surface concentration for the different species (e.g., hydrogen) at each latitude band, based on sparse observations. Since the real-world distribution of the gases is unlikely to be perfectly zonally symmetric (i.e., invariant around a band of latitude), concentration-based models likely add sources and sinks in places where there might not be sources/sinks. On the other hand, emission-driven models allow the different species to freely evolve in the atmosphere, implementing sources and sinks of hydrogen in places where exchanges are known to happen. The downside of this approach is that concentrations at the different latitudes are inevitably not effectively reproduced [7].

In the coming subsections, the above mentioned 3 research articles are going to be discussed and see what factors they have used to measure GWP of hydrogen. In the end, a conclusion will be reached, to

which GWP100 & GWP20 is most relevant to our study and for the further calculations in the coming sections.

3.3.1 H₂ causes indirect radiative forcing of $0.84 \text{ mW m}^{-2} / (\text{Tg}(\text{H}_2)\text{yr}^{-1})$

In the research of Fabien Paulot et al. [12], the representation of hydrogen is done with GFCL-AM 4.1 model which includes the updated emission inventories and improved representation of hydrogen soil removal, the dominant sink of hydrogen. From this research, it was found that the biggest uncertainties are related to the magnitude of anthropogenic and biomass burning hydrogen emissions. Comparison between different representation of soil hydrogen consumption, the dominant removal mechanism for atmospheric hydrogen, shows considerable differences in the tropics and subtropics, which reflects uncertainties in soil moisture and sensitivity.

Paulot et al. use emission-driven approach for hydrogen and ozone (O₃). In this model, the effect that an extra pulse of hydrogen has on the atmospheric chemistry over a certain period of time is monitored, allowing an estimate of the variation in the radiative forcing. The hydrogen budget for this model:

- A) Total tropospheric burden – 157.4 Tg (Range around 136 – 157 Tg H₂)
- B) Tropospheric lifetime – 2.1 years (Range between 1.9 – 2.3)

Using the model (and assuming linearity with the calculations), the suggested ERF efficiency of $0.84 \text{ mW m}^{-2} / (\text{Tg}(\text{H}_2)\text{yr}^{-1})$ or $0.13 \text{ mW m}^{-2}/\text{ppbv}$. The magnitude of this value is primarily controlled by changes in methane and stratospheric water vapour with a smaller contribution from increasing tropospheric ozone. Converting ERF to GWP100 results at around $11 \pm 5 \text{ kg CO}_2\text{e/Kg H}_2$ [7].

3.3.2 In earlier studies the GWP100 of hydrogen is found to be 5 ± 1

Derwent et al. [5] used the STOChem – CRI model to describe the global sources & sinks of hydrogen and its isotopomer (HD). The STOchastic CHEMistry model is a global Lagrangian three dimensional chemistry transport that was initially developed to describe the global distribution of ozone & methane. The newer version of the model has been expanded to the representation of the atmospheric chemistry of ozone, nitrogen oxides, CO, methane & a range of organic compounds and this version is called STOChem-CRI. The most important source of hydrogen is the photochemical oxidation of methane & other organic components. Using the enhanced version of the model helps for the global representation of hydrogen & HD. The hydrogen budget for this model:

- A) Total burden (Tg) – Estimated to be around 150 Tg (Range around 149 – 176 Tg)
- B) Atmospheric lifetime of Hydrogen – 1.5 years (Range around 1.4 – 2.7)

The model is able to satisfactorily describe the observed tropospheric distribution of hydrogen & HD. Once the model has been selected, then they go on to quantify the methane & ozone responses to emission pulses of hydrogen and their likely radiative forcing consequences.

Using the model, the radiative forcing consequence of hydrogen has been expressed on a 1Tg basis and integrated over a one year time horizon. When compared to the consequences of a 1 Tg emission pulse of CO₂, 1 Tg of hydrogen causes 5 ± 1 times as much time integrated radiative forcing over a 100 year time horizon. This is to say, hydrogen has a GWP100 of 5 ± 1 .

3.3.3 The GWP100 of hydrogen is found to be 11.6 ± 2.8 in the latest studies

In the study by Maria Sand et al [1], the GWP100 of hydrogen is estimated using five global atmospheric chemistry models (GFDL, OsloCTM, INCA, WACCM and UKCA). The GWP was calculated using a steady state perturbation approach that takes all effects of the atmospheric hydrogen into account in a

comprehensive way. The hydrogen budget calculated using the six models are shown in Figure 4. It shows the hydrogen budget for all the models:

- A) Total burden (in Tg) – Measured to be close to 200 Tg
- B) Total lifetime and atmospheric lifetime (in years) – Lifetime of hydrogen is around 2.4 years (1.9 – 2.7 years model range)

With the calculations from these models, the model mean hydrogen GWP100 is found to be 11.6 ± 2.8 (one standard deviation). The largest contribution is from changes in methane (44%), followed by ozone (38%) and stratospheric vapour (18%). This resulting number is comparable with:

- 1) The work done by Warwich et al., [16] showed that GWP100 for hydrogen is around 12 ± 6 .
- 2) The work done by Hauglustaine et al., [17] showed that GWP100 for hydrogen is around 12.8 ± 5.2 (90% confidence interval)

On the other hand, the result of this research is twice as high compared to the results of Derwent et al., (2006, 2018, 2020). This is because the other studies did not consider changes in the stratosphere but rather focused only on the tropospheric distributions. This research further calculated other time horizons: GWP20 (37.3 ± 15.1) and GWP500 (3.31 ± 0.98).

The largest uncertainty estimated by this model in the calculation of GWP100 is the soil uptake, which is also the largest term in the hydrogen budget, accounting for as much as 80% of the loss of hydrogen. Just this uncertainty alone, would contribute to a deviation/uncertainty of around ± 2.1 for GWP100.

3.3.4 GWP100 for hydrogen is taken as 11.6 ± 2.8 for this study

The above 3 models described GWP100 using different chemistry and soil deposition. The GWP figures are affected by a high level of uncertainty. In addition to the previous uncertainties, regarding hydrogen sources and sinks, a source of uncertainty is also with the limited timescale of the simulations. Additional source of uncertainty is the dependence of the lifetime on the emission latitude. Taking all the sources into consideration, combined with all the uncertainties, it shows the difficulties of picking a single GWP 100 number. However, the latest and most complete research estimates a GWP100 value of 11.6 ± 2.8 [1], [12] - [17], which will be used in this report for the calculations.

3.4 Consulted literature confirms that emissions from a leak-tight gas grid decrease when switching to hydrogen

A relevant paper regarding hydrogen transportation in pipelines and the emission of hydrogen was written by Hauglustaine et al. [17]. In this paper the climate consequences of a future hydrogen economy are presented. In Figure 4 one of the conclusions is placed in a matrix. On the x-axis a relevant timescale can be chosen (as an example: GWP100 corresponds to a 100 year time horizon). On the y-axis a leakage rate of the hydrogen value chain can be chosen, in this case meaning the amount of leaked gas divided by the total utilized gas. The number at the intersection of the chosen values is the percentage of CO₂ equivalent emissions that remains after the transition from natural gas to hydrogen. As hydrogen is a short-lived species in the atmosphere the shorter the time horizon the higher its GWP value. Therefore in Figure 4 the equivalent emission number is higher on the left side (short time horizon) than on the right side. With an increased leakage ratio, more hydrogen enters the atmosphere and therefore there is a rise in equivalent emissions. This can become problematic, especially at high leakage ratios and short time horizons. In Figure 4 it can be seen that at very high leakage ratios (>10%) and a short time horizon (one year), the transition to hydrogen can even lead to an increase in

greenhouse emissions. However, these kind of leakage rates are very excessive and it is expected that this can never be the situation in the Netherlands. Actual leakage ratios of a pipeline system based on methane losses in the Netherlands are around 0.1%. The leak rates in Figure 4: The GWP based equivalent emissions for hydrogen. Figure 4 [17] are based on leak rates in the entire value chain. This makes a direct comparison difficult, however the given equivalent emissions are in the same order as the numbers that are presented in chapter 2. The results also underline that an energy change from natural gas to green hydrogen gives a very big decrease in emissions.

Figure 4: The GWP based equivalent emissions for hydrogen. [17]

4. The hydrogen gas grid will be different than the current natural gas grid

As discussed previously, the grid in the future will be different than the current grid. The methane emission data is only available from past years, hydrogen will be utilized in the future. To bridge this gap an assumption is made on the future hydrogen grid. This is based on the “II3050 – editie 2” scenarios from NBNL [18]. In these scenarios the forecasted percentages of the hydrogen and natural gas grids are given.

4.1 The four scenarios of the II3050 give different grid lengths

The four scenarios are depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The four scenarios from II3050 further explained

In the scenarios and their differences which are important for this study can shortly be described as follows:

- Decentral initiatives (DEC)
 - This scenario focuses on a strong presence of decentralized production and local usage. The total hydrogen energy share in 2050 is expected to be 15%.
- National leadership (NAT)
 - This scenario focuses on a national policy driven by the government. The total hydrogen energy share in 2050 is expected to be 23%.
- European integration (EUR)
 - This scenario focuses on a European collaboration with the energy production centralised in certain areas of Europe. The total hydrogen energy share in 2050 is expected to be 15%.
- International trade (INT)

- This scenario focuses on international energy and material trading. The total hydrogen energy share in 2050 is expected to be 29%.

In paragraph 8.4.1 of the I13050 report it is described what percentage of the natural gas grid is removed in 2050 per scenario. The remaining grid is used for transportation of biomethane, or repurposed for hydrogen, the division is dependent on the scenario. These numbers are used to calculate the percentages of main lines, service lines and number of stations. As the numbers are only displayed in a graph, there is some readout error. Furthermore, the estimated number of the removed district stations is only available for two scenarios. For the other two scenarios they are interpolated. A distinguishment was made for the type of station; stations for end users scale with grid length while other stations scale with the given decrease. Using these numbers lead to Table 3.

Table 3: Percentages of remaining regional gas grid assets in 2050 for 4 different scenarios.

	DEC	NAT	EUR	INT
Percentage Main lines	32	65	78	90
Percentage Service lines	32	50	70	78
Percentage Stations	52	70	82	88
Hydrogen share	67	71	31	97

DSOs in the Netherlands typically use a high pressure main line (8 bar) for higher flows and longer lengths and a low pressure lines (100mbar) for distribution within neighbourhoods. Depending on the scenario, a different ratio between high pressure and low pressure pipeline is repurposed. For example, in the European scenario the high pressure lines are divided equally between green gas and hydrogen, whereas the majority of the remaining low pressure natural gas grid is used for the distribution of green gas. This division is not accounted for in the numbers, as it is proven difficult to incorporate. Without this division another error in the numbers is introduced, however it is believed that given the wide span of percentages, a reasonable estimation can be made.

A part of the distribution grid remains distributing methane, as (synthetic) natural gas, or as biomethane. The hydrogen share in the regional grids are shown in the last line [18]. If the hydrogen share is included, the percentages of distribution grid that is transporting hydrogen is even lower. The assumption hereby is that the percentages of the hydrogen grid scales linearly with the percentage of used hydrogen. The results can be seen in Table 4.

Table 4: The percentages of remaining regional gas grid transporting hydrogen in 2050 for different scenarios.

	DEC	NAT	EUR	INT
Percentage Main lines	21	46	24	87
Percentage Service lines	21	36	22	76
Percentage Stations	35	50	25	85

These percentages are incorporated into the methodology described in chapter 2: The emission numbers from the OGMP reporting, multiplied by their specific leak factors, and finally multiplied by the percentage of remaining of the grid. This gives the following amounts of hydrogen emission which can be expected in 2050 per scenario (Table 5).

Table 5: The hydrogen emission (in kg) of the regional grid operators for the different scenarios.

	DEC	NAT	EUR	INT
Hydrogen emission (kg)	569696	1140362	617979	2205092

It can be seen that different scenarios lead to different emissions for the DSOs. Overall, the emission is only a small part (~0.1%) of the total predicted transport, as is currently with natural gas transportation. Figure 6 shows the percentagewise distribution of the total hydrogen emission in the international scenario. It can be seen that service lines contribute the most, and stations the least.

Figure 6: Percentages on the origin of hydrogen emission

An overall conclusion on the emission numbers can be read in chapter 2.

4.2 Emissions from the transport grid are relatively low

Figure 7: The predicted hydrogen transport grid in 2050.

The Dutch gas TSO (Gasunie) presented rollout plan for the hydrogen backbone in July 2023 [19]. The map in Figure 7 shows the predicted end result of the hydrogen backbone in 2050. It consists of a north-south corridor in the east of the Netherlands, complemented by a pipe in the west to create a ring through the Netherlands and a ring through the North Sea. With this prediction an estimate can be made for the hydrogen grid length of the TSO. To determine the predicted emission, the same approach is made as for the DSOs. The current methane emission is used to come up with a leakage ratio per station or kilometre. This will be combined with the rollout plan specifying the length and other parameters in 2030 and 2050.

The current total reported methane emission of the Dutch transmission network is divided over several components:

- Compressor stations (38%)
- Transmission station (47%)
- LNG plants (14%)
- Underground storage (1%)
- Transmission grid (1%)

Note that the pipelines used in the transmission grid are made from steel, therefore permeation of the pipelines is negligible. To calculate the future hydrogen emissions some assumptions are made:

- In the 2030 scenario, it is foreseen that due to the limited demand, no compressor stations are needed. In the 2050 scenario compressor stations are needed. Currently there are two general types of compressor stations in use; natural gas powered and electric powered. Typically, the electric powered stations are newer and emit less methane. Gasunie indicates that future compressor stations will be electric powered and that hydrogen compressor stations should be emission free. However, this is not yet the case and to have the worst-case scenario (compressing hydrogen with current technology) the emission numbers of the current electrically powered stations (per Megawatt) are used in the 2050 scenario. It is expected that hydrogen compressor technologies will improve over the next two decades, both in efficiency as in leakage amount. This improvement is not incorporated into the calculations.
- In the hydrogen network, there will be transmission stations similar to the current stations in the natural gas network. It was chosen to keep the number of stations per kilometre equal to that of the current natural gas grid. Roughly two-third of the methane emissions are vented emissions (pneumatic devices, vents from gas analysers, and vents from operations). Gasunie plans to perform emission free operations, therefore these are not taken into account. It is uncertain if this can be the case for every operation (e.g. emergency vents). Therefore, emissions on maintenance, process and commissioning & decommissioning have been incorporated to create a worst-case scenario. The remaining one-third are small leakages in the stations and have been included as well.
- The currently existing LNG plant will not be a part of the hydrogen grid. Therefore their numbers will not be taken into account. There will be LH₂/NH₃ terminals in the future that produce gaseous hydrogen. It is uncertain if Gasunie will operate these, or that a third party will exploit these. Because of this uncertainty (both in number, size and operator) it was chosen not to take these into account. This creates an uncertainty in the total emission number.
- One of the advantages of hydrogen is the possibility to store energy underground. Underground storage will become an important factor to balance the hydrogen grid. For

hydrogen it is expected that these plants will have a large similarity to currently existing natural gas underground storage facilities. However, due to the plans of Gasunie, only the fugitive emissions are taken into account for the number of predicted storage facilities [20].

- The emissions from transmission pipelines are almost completely from operations on the grid. Although Gasunie plans to perform emission free operations, it is uncertain if this can be the case for every operation (e.g. emergency vents). Therefore, these maintenance and operation emissions have been incorporated, to create the worst-case scenario.

These assumptions are incorporated in the scenarios for 2030 and 2050. For 2030 the scenario is that in total 1200 km pipeline is operational, and one underground storage facility is active. Compressor stations are not required at this time. If these numbers are multiplied with the averaged hydrogen emitted per number or length, MW and storage facilities; a total of 13.000 kg H₂ emission per year is calculated.

In the scenario for 2050, the transport grids consists of 2200 km of pipeline, 440 MW of compressor stations power, and a total of 25 underground storage facilities. Using the same method of calculation, this gives 210.000 kg H₂ emission per year.

5. The hydrogen emissions decrease if mitigating measures are implemented

There are several methods to implement mitigating measures on hydrogen emission. These mitigating measures have many similarities to the methane emission mitigation measures. Future (hydrogen) gas grids will be installed while knowing the effects of emission of hydrogen. For the natural gas grid emission, sometimes installed decades ago, this only became important in recent years. This means that it can be expected that the hydrogen grid has less emission due to the insights in emission and emission behaviour of hydrogen. The leak tightness of the grids is also likely to improve due to improved operating procedures, technological advancements, new insights and improved materials. A quantification of this improvement was not found in the given scenarios. Also, after some research it was found that these are difficult parameters to estimate. Therefore, this future grid improvement is not taken into account in the calculations.

To mitigate the fugitive emissions, several actions can be taken:

- More frequent leak searching (LDAR)
 - A large share of the emissions is caused by small leakages that can linger on for a long period. The more frequent the leak searching is, the sooner leaks will be detected. Decreasing the time between leak searching makes a big impact on the fugitive emissions. It is expected that in the future legislation will promote more frequent leak searching.
- Focus of preventing 3rd party damages
 - 3rd party damages are one of the biggest emission sources. When looking at the factors from Table 1, it becomes clear that this emission source becomes more important to mitigate as their relative contribution increases with the transition to hydrogen. Preventing 3rd party damages is already a focus for grid operators, and prevention should be increased even more in the future.
- Phase out materials that are prone to leaking
 - Some pipeline materials (such as cast iron) are prone to leaking, for instance by cracking due to age. This increases fugitive emissions as well as that it poses a safety hazard. The grid operators are remediating these materials. If hydrogen is to be transported through a pipeline of such a material, the section should be replaced preferable before the hydrogen is transported. As of now, the Dutch grid operators working with hydrogen are operating in this manner.
- Adapt procedures to be leak free
 - Certain amounts of hydrogen are emitted during phasing in or out of hydrogen lines. Making sure that all these procedures are leak free, for instance using flaring instead of venting, or (even better) using recompression, will provide a positive benefit to the hydrogen emissions.

Decreasing permeation, for instance by changing pipeline materials (e.g. steel or multi-layered pipelines) or increasing wall thickness will also decrease fugitive emissions. The permeation of hydrogen is about 4 times as high as from methane. Although decreasing permeation by material choice might seem beneficial, the expected absolute gains with hydrogen are really small as permeation is only less than 1% of the total fugitive hydrogen emissions. As the current natural gas

grid can and will be largely reused, it does not make sense to replace the existing gas lines by lines made with less permeable material or increased wall thickness.

6. Appendix A: The IPCC standpoint on emission metrics

From IPCC AR6 [2] box 7.3:

“Physical Considerations in Emissions Metric Choice Following AR5, this Report does not recommend an emissions metric because the appropriateness of the choice depends on the purposes for which gases or forcing agents are being compared. Emissions metrics can facilitate the comparison of effects of emissions in support of policy goals. They do not define policy goals or targets but can support the evaluation and implementation of choices within multi-component policies (e.g., they can help prioritize which emissions to abate). The choice of metric will depend on which aspects of climate change are most important to a particular application or stakeholder and over which time horizons. Different international and national climate policy goals may lead to different conclusions about what is the most suitable emissions metric (Myhre et al., 2013b). Global warming potentials (GWP) and global temperature-change potentials (GTP) give the relative effect of pulse emissions, that is, how much more energy is trapped (GWP) or how much warmer (GTP) the climate would be when unit emissions of different compounds are compared (Section 7.6.1.2). Consequently, these metrics provide information on how much energy accumulation (GWP) or how much global warming (GTP) could be avoided (over a given time period, or at a given future point in time) by avoiding the emission of a unit of a short-lived greenhouse gas compared to avoiding a unit of CO₂. By contrast, the new metric approaches of combined GTP (CGTP) and GWP closely approximate the additional effect on climate from a time series of short-lived GHG emissions, and can be used to compare this to the effect on temperature from the emission or removal of a unit of CO₂ (Section 7.6.1.4; Allen et al., 2018b; Collins et al., 2020).*

If global surface temperature stabilization goals are considered, cumulative CO₂ equivalent emissions computed with the GWP-100 emissions metric would continue to rise when short-lived GHG emissions are reduced but remain above zero (Figure 7.22b). Such a rise would not match the expected global surface temperature stabilization or potential decline in warming that comes from a reduction in emissions of short-lived greenhouse gases (Pierrehumbert, 2014; Allen et al., 2018b; Cain et al., 2019; Collins et al., 2020; Lynch et al., 2020, 2021). This is relevant to net zero GHG emissions goals (Section 7.6.2 and Box 1.4). When individual gases are treated separately in climate model emulators (Cross-Chapter Box 7.1), or weighted and aggregated using an emissions metric approach (such as CGTP or GWP) which translate the distinct behaviour from cumulative emissions of short-lived gases, ambiguity in the future warming trajectory of a given emissions scenario can be substantially reduced (Cain et al., 2019; Denison et al., 2019; Collins et al., 2020; Lynch et al., 2021). The degree of ambiguity varies with the emissions scenario. For mitigation pathways that limit warming to 2°C with an even chance, the ambiguity arising from using GWP-100 as sole constraint on emissions of a mix of greenhouse gases (without considering their economic implications or feasibility) could be as much as 0.17°C, which represents about one-fifth of the remaining global warming in those pathways (Denison et al., 2019). If the evolution of the individual GHGs is not known, this can make it difficult to evaluate how a given global multi-gas emissions pathway specified only in CO₂ equivalent emissions would achieve (or not) global surface temperature goals. This is potentially an issue as Nationally Determined Contributions frequently make commitments in terms of GWP-100-based CO₂ equivalent emissions at 2030 without specifying individual gases (Denison et al., 2019). Clear and transparent representation of the global warming implications of future emissions pathways including Nationally Determined Contributions could be achieved either by their detailing pathways for multiple gases or by detailing a pathway of cumulative carbon dioxide equivalent emissions approach aggregated across GHGs evaluated by either GWP* or CGTP metric approaches (Cain et al., 2019; Collins et al., 2020; Lynch et*

al., 2021). It should be noted that although the Paris Agreement Rulebook asks countries to report emissions of individual GHGs separately for the global stocktake (Decision 18/CMA.1, annex, paragraph 38), which can allow the current effects of their emissions on global surface temperature to be accurately estimated, estimates of future warming are potentially ambiguous where emissions are aggregated using GWP-100 or other pulse metrics. Although there is significant history of using single-basket approaches, supported by emissions metrics such as GWP-100, in climate policies such as the Kyoto Protocol, multi-basket approaches also have many precedents in environmental management, including the Montreal Protocol (Daniel et al., 2012). Further assessment of the performance of physical and economics-based metrics in the context of climate change mitigation is provided in the contribution of Working Group III to AR6.”

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